

PROSPECTS OF TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT:

At present, the development of theoretical, methodological and practical approaches to solve the problems of sustainable development of national tourism in our republic, the formation of the market of tourist products, the economic methods of regulating the activities of this sector and the organizational structures of its management, and the improvement of the economic mechanism of tourism development are of great importance.

After the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, fundamental reforms are being carried out in all sectors of the economy. In particular, the State attaches great importance to the development of tourism. The main infrastructures that make up the tourism sector are: accommodation facilities, catering services and transport services. Based on this, transport services play a key role in the development of the tourism sector. The development and improvement of transport services creates convenience for tourists and eases their travel. Through this, it is possible to achieve the development of tourism in the country.

In order to further develop and improve the tourism sector in our country, in the future, actively attracting foreign investments, world brands,

creating favorable conditions for business in the tourism sector, modern facilities of tourism infrastructure, first of all, hotels, transport-logistics, are being built in all regions of our republic. It is important to build structures, engineering and communication facilities, in this process it is important to take into account that the new facilities fully meet international standards and the needs and demands of tourists.

In the organization of tourism services, first of all, comprehensive measures to ensure the safety of life and health of tourists and excursionists are implemented in places where tourists are accommodated, at food points, when moving around the territory of the republic, when organizing visits to tourism facilities. increase, rapid development of tourism in the country, more complete and effective use of the existing huge tourism potential, together with traditional cultural and historical tourism, other potential types of tourism - pilgrimage, ecological, educational, ethnographic, gastronomic, sports, treatment-health "localization, rapid development of rural, industrial, business tourism and other types, strengthening the social importance of tourism due to the development of children, teenagers and youth tourism, family tourism, social tourism for the elderly, establishing new tourism destinations in the regions, passporting them, The development and implementation of national and regional programs for the comprehensive development of domestic, inbound and outbound tourism, aimed at the formation of unified national registers of tourism destinations and tourism objects, requires international cooperation in the field of tourism activities, first of all, the UN World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), influential international and national organizations on tourism of foreign countries, expanding cooperation with active participants of regional and world markets of tourism services, participation of Uzbekistan in universal international conventions and agreements regulating the field of tourism, introduction of international and interstate standards and norms in the practice of tourism activities determined by the decisions made.

Speaking about the development of tourism infrastructure in Uzbekistan, it is important to dwell on the division of the country into main tourism regions. Today, there are four main tourist regions in the Republic, which are Fergana, Samarkand-Bukhara, Tashkent and Khorezm tourism regions. Fergana tourism region includes Fergana valley. Its touristic resources consist of archeological excavations and architectural monuments,

favorable natural conditions, products of traditional folk crafts and art, industrial and agrarian complexes. The presence of a wide network of roads and railways here also provides an opportunity to use the Fergana region for tourism purposes, to place tourism bases and recreation centers in its entire territory. Tashkent tourism region has universal opportunities for the development of all types of tourism in the future. Cultural monuments in this tourism region, today's life of the capital region, constructions, new cities and villages, modern culture, nature of the region, rich landscape, colorful flora and fauna are important factors that make it attractive. The network of automobiles and railways connects the tourism centers of the Tashkent tourism region with each other and allows the development of railway and automobile tourism around the city. Samarkand-Bukhara tourism region includes Samarkand, Bukhara and Navoi regions. The world-famous architectural monuments of Samarkand and Bukhara are the basis for the development of tourism in this region. In addition, the railway and wide network of highways passing through the Zarafshan River, low passes and good roads through the Zarafshan mountain range are very favorable factors for the development of tourism in the region. The potential of the Khorezm tourism region is mainly based on the rich historical and architectural monuments located in the Ichan Castle Reserve of Khiva, which is unparalleled in the world.

LIST OF REFERENCES

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 2, 2016 No. PF-4861 "On measures to ensure rapid development of the tourism sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan".
2. Yuldasheva , S. ., & Po'latova , O. . (2023). O'ZBEKISTONDA QISHLOQ XO'JALIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI. Инновационные исследования в современном мире: теория и практика, 2(10), 55–57. извлечено от <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/zdit/article/view/11574>
3. Yuldasheva Shaxnoza, Po'latova Odina. (2023). DIRECTIONS OF DEVELOPMENT OF AGRICULTURE IN UZBEKISTAN. DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATIONS IN SCIENCE, 2(3), 103–106. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7778314>
4. Yuldasheva Shaxnoza, Olimjonova Farogat. (2023). AGRICULTURAL DEVELOPMENT POTENTIAL. INNOVATIVE RESEARCH IN SCIENCE, 2(3), 66–70. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7778308>

5. Yuldasheva Shahnoza, Faxriddinova Dilobar. (2023). ORGANIZING NEW TOURISM DESTINATIONS IN UZBEKISTAN. INTERNATIONAL BULLETIN OF APPLIED SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY, 3(2), 182-184. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7683651>

6. Yuldasheva Shahnoza, Faxriddinova Dilobar. (2023). THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL ISSUES OF DETERMINING THE EFFICIENCY OF COTTON RAW PRODUCTION. INTERNATIONAL BULLETIN OF APPLIED SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY, 3(2), 58-61. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7620997>

7. Yuldasheva Shaxnoza, Ismatova Nigora. (2023). IMPROVING THE STATE SUPPORT SYSTEM OF THE COTTON NETWORK. SOLUTION OF SOCIAL PROBLEMS IN MANAGEMENT AND ECONOMY, 2(2), 187-191. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7676504>

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